

AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF THE COMMERCIALIZATION OF YOGA AND SKILL DEVELOPMENT OF YOUTH

Dr. Asha Rongali,

Department of Commerce,
Pandit Shiv Ram Government Degree College,
Tyuni, Dehradun
Email: rongaliasha@gmail.com

Prof. Kanchan Lata Sinha

Faculty of Commerce & Management,
Pt. L.M.S. Campus,
Sri Dev Suman Uttarakhand Vishwavidyalaya, Rishikesh
Email: drkanchanlata sinha123@gmail.com

Abstract

Skill Development is the productive capabilities acquired through all levels of learning and training during the period of learning since a child goes to a learning center from kindergarten to adult learning institutions. Yoga is a practice of physical mental and spiritual connection of a person, which is an ancient system adopted to improve mental power, physical strength, and spiritual connection with God. It is an expensive process that has gained unprecedented appreciation and popularity among all ages around the world. Earlier when it started gaining popularity it was recognized as a form of exercise only but since it proved the scientific base behind its all asanas it also found that it helps in improving mental activities, decision-making ability, strength, stamina, and much more. Today youth around the age of 15-24 years are battling with several mental issues, fear of neglect, failure, unacceptance, anxiety, and advanced mental health issues as well as emotional disorders. It was found in studies depression is the fourth leading cause of disability among adolescents aged 15-19 years and affects their studies and careers adversely. It is also found that excessive use of gadgets among youth like TV, mobile, tablet, computers, laptops, and internet-based Instruments also hamper the development of skills among youth.

As today's youth is battling with so many mental disorders and mental issues and the solution is only with performing yogic activities. Yoga is a life-changing practice that helps in boosting in mental stability, physical stamina, and spiritual connection with God. Performing various Asanas regularly will enhance the lung's capacity, and the reach of oxygen to the brain helps the nervous system to act in a better manner. Youth will find tremendous energy in performing routine activities as well as helpful in the development of skills like learning capacity, remembering, and decision-making activities as it enhances concentration and focus by just investing 20 minutes a day in

performing yogic asanas. This research paper will highlight the importance of yoga in commercializing and developing skills among the youths with regular performing of yogic asanas.

Keywords: Skill-development, Yogic-asanas, physical strength, mental well-being, commercial, economic development.

Introduction

Learning is the process of attaining new skills, behavior, values attitudes, and preferences. In this present scenario, the attainment of skills is necessary for the development of students whereas the ability to learn is the basic skill possessed by humans. Some of the learning patterns have been found in some animals and plants too.

There are many learning patterns available in established fields. i.e., educational, experimental, psychology, neuropsychology, etc. Learning can be habitual, heredity-based, or environmentally forced. Children are always excited about learning and new aspects of any learning patterns; few are developed with extraordinary skills to learn at a fast pace. Similarly in schools, skill development has attained a sharp high as is the present need of the hour for the economic development of the country with high earnings in less investment. That includes critical thinking, problem-solving, communication data analysis, rationalizing, etc. The required skills have differed with every different field of learning.

Uttarakhand is the state that is also known as the 'Abode of God' or the 'Land of God' and popularly known as the Yoga Capital of the world, Rishikesh is the Hub for Yoga, meditation, and Wellness. People from around the globe, visit here for yogic and wellness programs organized at Rishikesh every year. Many more destinations in India are highlighting their wellness and naturopathic value. In recent years the therapeutic value of Yoga and meditation has increased at a high rate.

One of the new dimensions was set by Yoga when it attained its popularity in the western countries whereas it was in the tradition and culture of the Indian soil. In a recent study, it was reported that around 192 countries celebrated Yoga Day, which shows the popularity and acceptance of Yoga as a global platform. Due to the present environment and timeless cutthroat competition, the students have to face many problems in learning and other daily learning activities and habits. Recent studies have found that Yoga is good for the mental and physical health of a person but this study will find out the importance of Yogic activities enhances the learning skills of a youth or a student and helpful in skill development as well.

Review of Literature

Robert G. Holly, in his study, highlighted that regular hatha yoga practices can have wonderful benefits in health-related aspects of physical fitness. That can be attained with regular yoga practices.

A, Malathi, et.al, highlighted in their studies that there is a beneficial effect of regular practice of Yoga on the well-being of a person that included 11 Subjective Well-Being Inventory.

Sat Bir S. Khalsa, also studied Yoga as a Therapeutic Invention and illustrated multiple practices, including exercise, breathing exercises, and meditation are the most comprehensive approaches in mind-body medicine and also help in stress management.

Nandani Bhalla, et.al., their studies investigated the content analysis of lifestyle advertisements in Yoga journal magazines and highlighted that the women of female featuring advertisements were more prevailing in the promotions of Yoga.

There is a dearth of research studies that have investigated the commercialization of Yoga and skill development of Youth and how it is contributing to the economic development of the youth as well. Very few studies have been taken so far concerning the significance of yogic activities in the skill development of the youth in the present scenario and also it will be helpful for academicians, educators, policymakers, research scholars, and students of all ages.

Objectives of the study

The object of the research study is enlisted as follows:

- To study the factors that positively contributed to the commercialization of yoga and the development of skills in the student.
- To enhance the learning skills of the students with yogic activities.
- To illustrate the changes in priorities of a student in the present scenario and adoption of Yoga Practices in their lifestyle.
- To investigate the yogic activities popular in younger generations and their impact on the monetary condition of the countr
- To highlight the positive impact of yogic activities in the skill development and economic development of society.

Research Methodology

For this research study, the researcher collected and referred to secondary data on *yoga*. The researcher had a descriptive study about the factors/ motivators that accelerate a desire to meditate in a particular place. A sincere effort has been made to find a way to create consistency in the growth and transformation of the youth in learning and skills development. The researcher referred to specific reports published by various national and state agencies/bodies such as the *Ministry of Tourism*, *Ministry of Ayush*, *Ministry of Commerce GOI*, etc. The author also studied various books published by renowned authors, websites, and research papers published in peer-reviewed journals to find out the previous work done in this area so far, and also acknowledged newspaper editorial columns based on Yoga and skill development and related issues.

Commercialization of Yoga in learning and Skill development in India

Yoga is an ancient and spiritual discipline based on scientific reasons and enlightens the body and mind. It is the art of living a sincere routine that follows from early rising to timely sleep. The word Yoga is derived from the Sanskrit word 'Yuj' which means join together or unite. It unites our body with our mind. It's a means to self-awareness and self-realization.

The various fossils that remain have been found in the Indus Valley civilization with figures performing yogic activities that show the existence of Yoga in ancient times. A few of the sources that confirm the existence of Yoga in ancient times were the Vedas, Upanishads, Puranas Epics, etc.

Traditional yoga became one of the commodities that are selling worldwide or being consumed at the global level. Then its importance is felt at all levels of management in different fields. In modern times special sessions take place at every institution in respect of stress management whether it's a School, college, professional institutes, training institutes, or other institutions of national importance requiring sessions in respect of stress management.

In the present scenario, today's youth is battling with many mental disorders and mental issues due to abnormal lifestyles, unhealthy food habits, excessive social media usage internet addiction pollution, etc. The solution is only being involved in physical activities. However, the physical activities involved less enthusiasm to perform due to being living in auto work time. Therefore, performing yogic activities not only enhances physical activities as well as helpful in the economic benefits of the younger generation. Yoga is a life-changing practice that helps boost mental stability, physical stamina, and spiritual connection with God, besides contributing to economic development. The main logic behind performing yogic activities or various Asanas regularly, it will enhance the lung's capacity, and the reach of oxygen to the brain helps the nervous system to act in a better manner and also enhances the capacity building of an individual.

Government Initiative in Commercialising Yoga

On 27th September 2014, the nation India urged to International Community for the adoption of International Day of Yoga. That day, world realised that Yoga is not only a building stone or uniting model of Mind and Soul but a Changing lifestyle not only helps an individual, society, or nation but the whole globe will benefit from battling with climate change as well. Therefore, it was not only commercialized but the whole globe will be benefitted from the economic and environmental benefits.

Three types of Yoga typically exist Material Yoga, Spiritual Yoga, and Transcendental Yoga. Earlier the Guru Shishya Parampara prevailed in ancient India and there was an emergence of different schools with their practices, approaches, and Philosophy. These schools were known as Jnana Yoga, Bhakti Yoga, Karma Yoga, Patanjali Yoga, Hatha Yoga, Jain Yoga, Buddha Yoga, Laya Yoga, Kundalini Yoga, Mantra Yoga, etc. due it's their scientific base and approach the World Health

Organisation collaborated with the Ministry of Ayush, Government of India for the medicine and wellness program.

Various capacity building Workshop or webinars on Yoga and related issues like Yoga benefits in Diabetes and hypertension, Yogic Management in Cancer, Bronchial Asthma and stroke, Yoga and Non-Communicable diseases, and several more initiatives have been conducted by the Government of India to aware people with facts of yoga in a particular scenario.

Scientific Approach to Yoga Practices

A few of the misconceptions prevailed about Yoga. Therefore, some of the misconceptions and factual truths need to be brought to notice and are illustrated in the following Table 1.1 below.

Table 1.1

Misconceptions and Facts in respect of Yogic activities

S. No	Misconception	Facts/logic
1.	Yoga is a ritual-based magic	Yoga is a philosophy and science for leading a happy and satisfied life.
2.	Yoga is an organized religion.	Yoga is a practical science dealing with universal truths about existential realities. It does not talk about any religion in particular. The elements of Yoga are found in many religious practices.
3.	Asanas and Physical exercises are the same.	There are definite differences and distinctions between both concerning aims, objectives, and the outcome of their practice at the level of consciousness.
5.	Only healthy persons can practice Yoga.	Yoga can be practiced by healthy and unhealthy people equally.
6.	Yoga practices are meant to reduce weight.	Yoga is good for the management of weight and other health-related issues.
7.	Yoga practices can be practiced anywhere and anytime	There are certain rules to be properly followed in the beginning while practicing Yoga.

Source: Ministry of Ayush, Government of India

Table 1.1 shows the factual findings published by the Ministry of Ayush, Government of India concerning Yoga practices and prevailing concepts brought factual information about Yoga practices

and its benefits that can be reaped by the individuals. It was observed in the past that after the COVID-19 outbreak, the majority of students of different ages have been impacted in learning skills and concentration drastically, and their performance in learning and skill-based power had reduced several folds. Therefore, to recover from this situation many of them adopted Yoga practices in their family regularly and found positive results.

Yoga for the Skill Development in the Youth

A large percentage of the population consists of people aged between 10-24 years who are popularly known as adolescents and young adults and adults and comprise nearly 25% of the population they have a distinct pattern of health issues that varies to their environment, family, society and personal aptitude level, and in the present scenario, they are living in such environment where competition is so high with less chance of success in their fields due to lifestyle changes, food habits, family upbringing, social attitudes and influences and so on.

According to the Adolescence report published by the Ministry of Ayush, Government of India, Yoga comprises eight aspects moral discipline, social discipline, extension and expansion of the life force, involution of the senses, concentration, meditation, and the state of bliss. Therefore, when these aspects of the adolescents are controlled in an efficient and controlled manner, then their skills and abilities can be developed with efficiency and perfection. Therefore, skills can be imparted with yogic actions when it was adopted into routine by the concerned individuals.

Their willpower and endurance can be enhanced with specific asanas and can improve tolerance as well which will be helpful in stress management while studying, preparing for competitions, and career-building aspects. Yoga asanas practices will enhance the analytical and intellectual capabilities of youth as well. Thus, fruits can be reaped with higher benefits soon with yoga practices. Therefore, the following skills development aspect can be generated with Yoga practices by the younger adults/adults.

- Courage and Confidence
- Humanity and Humility
- Attainment of Efficiency
- Attainment of Multi-tasking Abilities
- Enhances sensitivity and emotional stability
- Ability to troubleshoot and problem-solving
- Discrimination and clarity
- Analytical and intellectual capabilities
- Observation and concentration
- Willpower and endurance

According to the report published by the Ministry of Ayush in respect of mental health and mental well-being of a person yogic activities are very beneficial in the long run. A survey in the year 2017 by The National Institute of Mental Health (NIMH) suggested that 10.6% of the population is suffering from only health problems. Therefore, the diagnosis is required to be separately identified so that the cause and remedies can be applied to solve the mental issues of every person suffering. Negligence of that impacted the adolescents/adults' behavior patterns in learning and skills development in the longer run.

Economic Aspects of Yoga Being Commercialised as a Commodity

According to one of the chief investment officers of “MarketsMojo” once incorporate a few good practices like Yoga and meditation which can solve 90% of our daily problems. In recent years the growth and popularity of Yoga have gone up several folds. It has been considered a commodity since its commercialization. Being it has its religious aspects and roots still it manages its front to manage as own kind of business concerning learning and teaching skills, fitness and wellness, nature health, yoga and trekking, yoga and naturopathy, yoga exercise accessories market, Yoga outfits market, Yoga and dietary market and much more.

Yoga was not popular in India but it had flied to western countries as well. According to the report published in (Ipsos Public Affairs,2016), it was found that in 2014 the number of yoga practitioners was 20.4 million which registered an increase and reached 37 million in 2016 in the United States. This shows the increasing popularity of Yoga in Western countries. Western people have more consumerism concerning Yogic activities and the Yoga Business popularity. Because of its health benefits people are attracted to and adopting the lifestyle recommended in Yoga Activities an essential phenomenon and practice. Yoga has become an essential commodity for consumers worldwide, therefore has a good share of the market for Yoga activities selling products from Education to Neuropathic medicinal treatment with Ayurveda.

In the present and the future time Yoga will not only be an exercise for the physical and mental well-being of a person but also an essential luxury and Exotic commodity that secures some social prestige and elite figure of society. This suggests a great market for the future to look into Yoga and Yoga related practices which were discussed above have well defined and well-designed market as an exotic and luxurious Commodity. Being popular with adults and the younger generation will capture the market hold in higher percentage in the Indian market as well and due to skill-based it will also enhance the economic contribution in respect of national income and foreign exchange. The wellness market is estimated at INR 490 billion and 40% of the market comprises Yoga and fitness studios alone, there is an estimation of another 20% increase and significant growth in the market size of Yoga and Meditation in the next three years and will reach to INR 875 billion

Key Findings and Suggestions

- It is found that today's youth is battling with so many mental disorders and mental issues and the solution is beheld with engaging in physical activities, here the best suited is the Yoga activities.
- There is a lot of pressure on the present youth to excel in every field, to find solutions to their problems related to future career aspects, and compatible with the present competitive environment.
- After the COVID-19 outbreak, the majority of students of different ages have been impacted in learning skills and concentration, to recover from this situation one has to practice yoga regularly.
- Regular and routine practice of Yoga activities enhances the economic activities directly and indirectly.
- Yoga activities have an importance in mental well-being as well as the economic impact through skill development in various fields.
- 10.6% of the population is suffering from only health problems. Therefore, the diagnosis is required to be separately identified so that the cause and remedies can be applied to solve the mental issues of every person suffering.
- Yoga is good for the mental and physical health of a person but this study will find out the importance of Yogic activities in enhancing the learning skills of a youth or a student and helpful in skill development as well.
- Yoga, has become an essential commodity for consumers worldwide, therefore has a good share of the market concerning Yoga activities selling products from Education to Neuropathic medicinal treatment with Ayurveda.
- In 2014 yoga practitioners 20.4 million which registered an increase and reached 37 million in 2016 adults in the United States. This shows the increasing popularity of Yoga in Western countries as well as the attainment of newer markets in foreign lands.
- Being popular with adults and younger generations will capture the market hold in higher percentage in the Indian market as well and due to skill-based it will also enhance the economic contribution in respect of national income and foreign exchange.

Conclusion

India has a great opportunity to excel in Yoga and related markets worldwide as Yoga has successfully registered itself as a different but essential commodity for the upliftment of health, wealth, and luxury in life. Therefore, Yoga is not only a business opportunity but a complete Business

package that has related fields of Yogic activities at domestic as well as foreign land with a huge amount of wealth creation in respect of domestic and foreign exchange and being at skill development it has ample opportunity to perform learning and teaching skills, fitness and wellness, nature health, Yoga and trekking, Yoga and naturopathy, Yoga exercise kit market, Yoga outfits market, Yoga and dietary market etc.

References

- Muktibodhananda, swami. (1993). *Hatha Yoga Pradipika*. Munger: Yoga Publication Trust.
- Iyenger, B. K.S (1993). *Light on the Yoga Sutras of Patanjali*. Aquarian Thorsons- An imprint of Harper Collins Publishers, London.
- Iyenger, B.K.S. (2013). *Tree of Yoga*. London: Harper Collins.
- Consumer Information on Proper Use of Yoga, Ministry of Ayush, Government of India.
- Yoga for Adolescents, Ministry of Ayush, Government of India.
- Yoga for Mental Health, Ministry of Ayush, Government of India.
- Ministry of Ayush, Government of India. 2016. *Common Yoga Protocol: International Day of Yoga, 21st June*. New Delhi.
- Kenneth Liberman, University of Oregon, USA. *Yoga Tourism in India*
- Om Prakash, *Yoga: Individual Prosperity and Indian Trade Opportunities*.
- www.yoga.ayush.gov.in
- www.economictimes.com/markets
- www.wikipedia.org
- Hoornweg, D., & Thomas, L. (n.d.). *What a waste: Solid waste management in Asia*. The World Bank.